

Conductometric and Spectrometric Studies on the Complexes of Ag(I) and Hg(II) with 1-Phenyltetrazoline-5-Thione

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Ag(I) and Hg(II) form stable complexes with 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thione (IPT5TH). Their complexation has been studied in solution by conductometric titration method and the solid complexes formed were separated, analysed and their structures have been suggested on the basis of infrared spectroscopic and conductometric methods. The experimental results indicate that both the ions form 1 : 1 polymeric complexes having formula $[Ag(IPT5TH)_nO]_n$ and $[Hg(IPT5TH)_xCl_2O]_x$ where n may be larger than x . The coordination number of Ag(I) ion and that of Hg(II) ion is 4. Both the complexes are bonded to the central metal ions both through nitrogen as well as sulphur. Simultaneous bonding through S- and N- has resulted in the considerable decrease in the intensity of the νNH band, disappearance of thioamide band I, splitting of the thioamide band II, reduction in intensity of thioamide band III and disappearance of thioamide band IV, on complexation.

COMPOUNDS containing a thioamide moiety

$H-N-C=S$ have been studied by several workers and it has been suggested that all such compounds give rise to four thioamide bands¹⁻⁴ in their IR spectra. They are all mixed bands and have contributions from $\delta N-H$, $\nu C=N$, $\nu C=S$ and $\delta C-H$. The bond order higher than one for $C=N$ and less than two for $C=S$ arise because of the following equilibrium :

The four thioamide bands appear around 1550 (band I), 1250 (band II), 900-1050 (band III) and 750-850 cm^{-1} (band IV) and these have contributions from ($\delta N-H + \delta C-H$), ($\delta N-H + \delta C-H + \nu C=N$), ($\nu C=N + \nu C=S$) and $\nu C=S$ respectively.

It has been reported that for monodentate sulphur ligands (such as thiocyanate ion), band IV ($\nu C=S$) may be used as diagnostic of metal ligand bonding⁵⁻²². Metal-sulphur bonding results in red shift of about 50 cm^{-1} in the thioamide band IV and metal nitrogen bonding generally results in either no shift or blue shift of the order of 30-40 cm^{-1} in this band. A red shift of the order of about 100 cm^{-1} in the thioamide band IV is an indication of a bridging system²³⁻²⁵. 1-Phenyltetrazoline-5-thione contains one imino group, one thiocarbonyl group and three other nitrogen atoms for coordination. Hence it can act as a monodentate or bidentate ligand. It exists as a thione form (Fig. Ia) and also in thiol form (Fig. Ib) in solution²⁶.

However, the IR spectra of 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thione (IPT5TH) does not show the S-H peak in the region of 2500 cm^{-1} . The UV and visible spectra of the ligand also indicate the presence of a $\nu C=S$ group in 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thione. Lieber *et al*²⁷ have shown that thiocarbonyl group of 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thione is electron withdrawing and the hydrogen linked with nitrogen atom at the four position of the heterocyclic ring is acidic.

The present work deals with conductometric studies and complexing behaviour of Ag(I) and Hg(II) ions with 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thione. It also deals with the separation of the complexes and their characterisation by spectroscopy and magnetic moment measurement. The nature of shifts in the thioamide bands corresponding to nature of metal-ligand bonding has also been examined herein.

Experimental

All chemicals used in this work were of AnalaR quality.

Method for Preparation of Ligand and Complexes :

1-Phenyltetrazoline-5-thione :

Phenylisothiocyanate was prepared by method given in the literature²⁸ and 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thione was prepared by the method of Lieber *et al*²⁹. The ligand was recrystallised from ethanol. The molecular formula of 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thione (1PT5TH) is $C_7H_6N_4S$ (molecular weight = 178). The analytical results of the ligand are given below :

Found : C, 46.88 ; H, 3.35 ; N, 30.45%
Calcd : C, 47.03 ; H, 3.39 ; N, 31.25%

1-Phenyltetrazoline-5-thionato aquo silver(I) polymer :

Silver nitrate and 1PT5TH were dissolved separately in ethanol and mixed in 1 : 2 molar ratio which formed immediate precipitate of the white complex. The complex was digested on water bath for about 30 minutes and filtered. It was washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in an oven at 110°. The analytical results of this complex are given below :

Found : N, 18.90 ; Ag, 35.00%
Calcd. : N, 18.48 ; Ag, 35.65%

Aquochloro 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thionato mercury (II) :

Mercuric chloride and 1PT5TH were dissolved separately in ethanol and mixed in 1 : 2 molar ratio which formed immediate precipitation of the white complex. The complex was digested on water bath for about 30 minutes and filtered. It was washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in an oven at 110°. Its analytical data are given below :

Found : N, 13.66 ; Hg, 46.14 ; Cl, 8.13%
Calcd. : N, 13.02 ; Hg, 46.52 ; Cl, 8.24%

Magnetic Measurement :

The magnetic measurement was done by Guoy balance at room temperature. These complexes were found to be diamagnetic.

Infrared Spectra :

The infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in KBr pellets using Perkin-Elmer model 621 infrared spectrophotometer in the range of 4000 to 200 cm^{-1} .

Conductometric Titrations :

Conductometric titrations were carried out by means of Sistrionic conductometer model 302.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results of the Ag(I) complex indicate that its stoichiometry is $Ag(1PT5T)H_2O$ and that of the mercury(II) complex is $HgCl(1PT5T)H_2O$.

The conductometric titration of the ligand with the metal ions Ag(I) and Hg(II) was conducted as discussed below :

The following stock of solutions were prepared :

- 50 cc (0.005M) solution of ligand in aqueous ethanol.
50 cc (0.01M) $AgNO_3$ solution in aqueous ethanol.
- 50 cc (0.005M) solution of ligand in ethanol.
50 cc (0.01 M) solution of $HgCl_2$ in ethanol.

10 cc of the ligand solution (0.005 M) in aqueous ethanol was taken in the conductivity cell and 1 cc of the $AgNO_3$ solution was added each time and the conductivity recorded.

The results in case of Ag(I) complex show an increase in conductivity from 0.55×10^3 in Mohs cm^2 to 0.70×10^3 Mohs cm^2 . The inflexion point at 5 ml is indicative of 1 : 1 complex having been formed and this agrees well with the composition of the solid complex.

In case of Hg(II) complex the conductivity measurements also show an inflexion at 5 ml indicative of a 1 : 1 complex.

Infrared Spectra :

The infrared spectral bands of the ligand and the complexes are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—INFRARED BANDS OF THE LIGAND AND COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

(1PT5TH)	[Ag(1PT5T)- (H ₂ O) _n]	[HgCl(1PT5T)- H ₂ O] _x	Assignments
—	3560 bm 3480 sh	3440 bm	H ₂ O
3080 bs 2950 bw	3060 vw 2920 vw	3060 vw 2020 vw	νN-H + νC-H in ligand but νC-H in complexes
—	1615 vs 1597 s 1512 vs	1615 bw 1595 m —	δH ₂ O Thioamide band I
1490 vs 1457 m	1490 s 1455 m	1495 s 1455 vw	
1383 m 1351 s 1327 m	1400 s 1370 vs 1340 vw	1400 sh 1370 s 1340 s	
1305 w 1295 w	1310 m 1295 w	1310 w 1295 vw	
1280 s	1280 w doublet 1270 m	1270 vw	Thioamide band II
1210 s 1175 w	1230 s 1170 m	1230 m 1170 vw	
1100 m	1110 s doublet 1100 s	—	
1090 m 1070 m	1080 vw 1070 m	1085 vw 1060 w	
1045 vs	1040 m	1045 w	Thioamide band III
1013 vw	1015 s	1015 m	
1000 m 985 vs 903 m 823 vw	990 m 910 m 830 vw	985 vw 910 vw 795 w	
785 m	—	—	Thioamide band IV
763 vw 750 s	755 vs 715 m	750 s —	
673 s 659 s	693 s doublet 693 s	692 s doublet 692 s	
573 vs 510 m 450 s 415 s	562 m 500 w 430 mb	565 m 496 vw 467 m 460 m	
390 w 350 w	390 vw 334 sh	370 vw 332 vw	
337 w	300 w	—	
323 w 320 m 310 m 295 vw 292 vw 257 vw	250 sh 240 vw 220 vw	250 s — 220 w	

changes have occurred in infrared spectral bands of the ligand on complexation with Ag(I) and Hg(II) ions. Some of the important changes are described below :

(a) Two very broad and medium bands are observed at 3560 and 3480 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the Ag(I) complex and one broad and medium band is observed at 3440 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the Hg(II) complex. The spectrum of the ligand does not contain any band in this region. Thus, the presence of these bands indicate the presence of coordinated water in these two complexes. Coordinated water molecule has its νOH mode of vibration in this region^{3,6-8,9}.

(b) There is no infrared band in the 1600 cm⁻¹ to 1700 cm⁻¹ region in the spectrum of the ligand. But a very strong band is present at 1615 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the Ag(I) complex and a weak broad band is present at 1615 cm⁻¹ in the Hg(II) complex. These bands may be due to H₂O mode of the coordinated water in the complexes. The strong intensity of the 1615 cm⁻¹ band in Ag(I) complex may be due to the polymeric nature of the Ag(I) complex, [Ag(1PT5T)(H₂O)_n] and the low intensity of the 1615 cm⁻¹ in Hg(II) complex, [Hg(Cl)(1PT5T)H₂O]_x due to its less degree of polymerisation than in [Ag(1PT5T)(H₂O)_n].

(c) There is a new medium broad band at 430 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of Ag(I) complex and a very weak absorption at this position in Hg(II) complex. They may be assigned to the librational mode of coordinated water molecule as no such band is present in the spectrum of the ligand. This is also supported by the fact that librational mode of coordinated water has been assigned in this region^{3,4,8,9}.

(d) There is a broad and strong band in the ligand at 3080 cm⁻¹ which has been assigned to νN-H and νC-H modes of vibration. This band shifts to 3060 cm⁻¹ in the Ag(I) and Hg(II) complexes with drastically reduced intensity. The reduction in intensity of this band on complexation is so large that only very weak band exists at 3060 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. This may be taken as a proof for the replacement acidic hydrogen of the ligand by means of metal ion as shown below :

Fig. 3.

A comparison of the infrared spectral bands of the ligand and the complexes indicate that a lot of

(e) Normal coordinate analysis of organic compounds containing a thioamide group ($\text{H}-\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{S}$) has been reported in the earlier literature. Agarwala and Rao³⁶ on the basis of normal coordinate analysis of ethylenethiourea molecule has suggested that the thioamide band I observed in the region of 1500 cm^{-1} is a mixed band having contributions from δNH (68 to 80%) and νCN (12 to 20%). The thioamide band II observed in the 1200 cm^{-1} region have contributions from $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ (36%) + νCN (30%) + δNH (24%). The thioamide bands III observed in the region of $900\text{--}1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have main contributions from $\nu\text{C}-\text{C}$ (24 to 34%) + $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ (19 to 26%) + νCN (15-34%). The band IV observed in the region of 700 cm^{-1} possesses main contributions from $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ (30%) + νCN (46%) + ring vibrational mode (11%). On the basis of the normal coordinate analysis of the tetrazole molecule and taking into consideration Agarwala and Rao³⁶ assignments of the thioamide bands, it seems reasonable to make the following assignments of the four thioamide bands of 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thione³² (Table 2).

Thioamide bands	I	II	III	IV
	1512 s	1280 s	1045 s	785 m
Assignments	$(\delta\text{NH} + \nu\text{CN})$	$(\nu\text{C}=\text{S} + \nu\text{C}-\text{N} + \delta\text{NH})$	$(\nu\text{C}-\text{C} + \nu\text{C}=\text{S} + \nu\text{CN})$	$(\nu\text{CS} + \nu\text{CN} + \text{ring deformation})$

(f) A comparison of the positions and intensities of the thioamide bands of the ligand and the complexes (Table 1) indicates that thioamide band I observed at 1512 cm^{-1} as a strong band in the infrared spectrum of the ligand disappears on complexation. Thus, there are two bands in the $1500\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand but there is only one band in this region of the complexes. This may be taken as an additional proof of replacement of acidic hydrogen of NH group of the ligand by means of Ag(I) ion in Ag(I) complex and by Hg(II) ion in Hg(II) complex as shown in Fig. 3.

The thioamide band II observed as a strong band at 1280 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand gets split in the Ag(I) complex and the split bands are observed at 1280 cm^{-1} as a weak band and at 1270 cm^{-1} as a medium band. This band is observed at 1270 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the Hg(II) complex as a very weak band. Slight lower shift and reduction in intensity of this band may be accounted for the coordination of the ligand to the metal ions through sulphur also. The reduction in intensity may be due to the fact that contribution of $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ mode has been removed from this band due to the coordination of the ligand to the metal ions through sulphur. Similar explanation can be given for the reduction of intensity of the thioamide band III on

complexation of the ligand with metal ions (Table 1).

The thioamide band IV is observed at 785 cm^{-1} as a medium band (Table 1). This band has almost disappeared from the spectra of the Ag(I) and Hg(II) complexes. As this band has major contribution from $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ mode of vibration and also because coordination has taken place through sulphur also, this band has been shifted to lower frequency and has probably merged with the 755 cm^{-1} strong band of the Ag(I) complex and 750 cm^{-1} strong band of the Hg(II) complex.

The above discussion indicates that 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thione is coordinated to the Ag(I) and Hg(II) ions through nitrogen as well as sulphur and water is coordinated to the metal ions. Thus, the following structures may be suggested to these complexes :

Fig. 4. Probable structure of $[\text{Ag}(\text{1PT5T})\text{H}_2\text{O}]_n$.

Fig. 5. Probable structure of $[\text{HgCl}(\text{1PT5T})\text{H}_2\text{O}]_x$.

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